

Applying model of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process to improve student character

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Abstract

The aim of this classroom action research is to improve student character through model of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process for 30 students Grade five at Cempaka Putih Timur 03 Public Elementary School in Jakarta in Indonesia. This research was composed of two cycles in applying model of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process at URL: <https://webpanduan.8b.io> consisting of character values integration in the beginning, core, and closing activities in teaching learning process. The results confirmed that student character in cycle 1 and 2 achieved 70.18 % and 83.82 %. It can be stated in conclusion that applying model of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process can improve student character for 30 students Grade five at Cempaka Putih Timur 03 Public Elementary School in Jakarta in Indonesia.

Keywords: *Mobile web; character building; teaching learning process; student character*

1. Introduction

Character education could be a high priority focus related to teacher preparation during the accreditation process (Jones, R & Bohlin, 2012). Character building can be done through culture, rules, regulations, events and ceremonies to give supportive examples of good habits for students (Izfanna and Hisyam, 2012). Developing student character can be done through character value integration of the activities done in teaching learning process (Marini, Maksum, Satibi, Edwita, Yarmi, & Muda, 2019). However, the previous studies do not combine character building with Information Communication and Technology including mobile web.

2. Literature review

Character education did not receive a high priority in the teacher education curriculum (Jones, R & Bohlin, 2012). This study found that character education was part of the mission in most private institutions. The method conducted to implement character education at Darunnajah Islamic boarding school was relied on knowledge, conditional methods and practices (Izfanna & Hisyam, 2012). Character building was applied through the formal subjects consisting of Akhlaq content, Islamic theology, Qur'an, Hadith, Fiqh, Mahfuzhat, Muthala'ah and Ushuluddin). Character value integration into preparation activities of teaching learning process is encouraged by praying, associating teaching material given with improvement of student positive attitude, and examining the neatness of student uniform (Marini, Maksum, Satibi, Edwita, Yarmi, & Muda, 2019). Character value integration into the core activities of teaching learning process is influenced by guiding the students to cooperate one another in group task, motivating the students to ask questions bravely, and taking priority of building student attitude. Character value integration into closing activities of teaching learning process is promoted by praying together, greeting between teacher and students. Fahmy, Bachtiar, Rahim and Malik (2015) found that building implementation in religious values occurred through attitudes and behaviors related to the tendency to be obedient to the teachings of one's religion, tolerant of others and live harmoniously with other religions (Fahmy, Bachtiar, Rahim and Malik, 2015). Character building was integrated in the curricula and was part of the school mission statements realized in school culture (Meidl & Meidl, 2013). Hidden curricula through social and cultural activities encouraged the process of character building related to the quality of interpersonal communication between students, including respect, equality, helpfulness, trust and honesty (Cubukcu, 2012). Character value integration process was applied in teaching learning process involving preparation, core, and closing activities, school culture consisting of religious, clean and healthy, nationalism, and working ethos, extracurricular activities, including rewards and facilities provided and community involvement including character building program and solving

character problems (Marini, MS, Maksum, Satibi, Yarmi, & Wahyudi, 2019; Oktarina, Widiyanto, and Soekardi, 2015; Marini, Maksum, Edwita, Satibi, & Kaban, 2019). Character values integrated into religious school culture by providing worship facilities, religious ceremonies and religious symbols encouraged the religious character of the students encouraged by obedience in carrying out the teachings of one's religions, the practice of religious tolerance towards others and living in harmony with other religions (Marini, Safitri, & Muda, 2018). However, most of previous studies has not integrated character building with Information Communication and Technology including mobile web.

3. Method

This classroom action research included planning, acting, observing, and reflecting steps in the spiral model by Kemmis and McTaggart to develop student character for 30 students Grade five at Cempaka Putih Timur 03 Public Elementary School in Jakarta in Indonesia. In the step of planning, lesson plan was created connected with applying model of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process. In the step of acting, applying model of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process in two cycles related to preparation, core, and closing activities of teaching learning process. In the step of observing, student character due to applying model of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process were recorded. In the step of reflecting, evaluation was made connected with the success of student character because of applying model of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process and this research was continued to the next cycle if the target of student character improvement established 80 % not achieved. The cycles done in this research can be seen in Figure 1.

4. Results and Discussion

In the step of planning, lesson plan of applying model of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process was created. In acting step, applying model of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process with URL: <https://webpanduan.8b.io> was related to preparation, core, and closing activities of teaching learning process. Character building in preparation activities of teaching learning process of mobile web model consisted of teacher presence on time, guiding students to pray according their respective religions before starting learning, checking the number of students being present and absent in class and clarifying the reason of student absence, inspecting the student neatness, being well-dressed and polite, asking the students greeting each other before apperception done, asking about nutritional balance of student breakfast menu, encouraging students to start learning, motivating students to study hard, preparing lesson plan incorporating character values, asking students to sing 'Garuda Pancasila' to instill nationalism values, conveying learning objectives by integrating relevant character values, and putting learning media so that students can see it to improve their learning motivation.

Character building in core activities of teaching learning process of mobile web model involved the teacher linking student competency standards and basic competences achieved with relevant character values, modifying teaching material by entering relevant character values, giving the opportunity to ask all students equally, giving questions requiring open answers to improve student creativity, giving equal attention to all students, grouping students in order to improve cooperation competences, accompanying students in group discussion to maintain that there are no students dominating in group, not giving final answers to students asking questions, being facilitator and motivator in class, creating a pleasant and conducive classroom atmosphere, giving appreciation to students who can answer the questions correctly, giving educative punishment to students violating the classroom rules, providing opportunity for students to answer other student questions, and using learning media that can increase student activities in learning.

Figure 1. The cycles of research

Character building in closing activities of teaching learning process of mobile web model included the teacher displaying student works in class to improve student enthusiasm, together with the students concluding the learning done by integrating relevant character values, giving evaluation in cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects, and giving the students opportunity to check their answers by themselves in order to instill student honesty values.

In observing step, student character related to student love of learning, perseverance, and prudence due to the effect of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process was recorded. In reflecting step, evaluation was made related to the success of student character improvement caused by applying model of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process. In cycle 1 and 2 the student character associated with the student love of learning in activities of the students doing homework, doing assignments, and listening to the teacher explanation reached 67.85 % and 85.62 %. The student perseverance in activities of the students finishing homework completely, being diligent to learn, and defending their argument in class debate attained 70.23 % and 83.34 %. The student prudence in activities of the students being happy to learn from other students, thinking thoroughly before doing something, and trying as much as possible to prove

the truth of information arrived at 72.46 % and 82.50 %. As a whole, the student character in cycle 1 and 2 achieved 70.18 % and 83.82 %. Due to the student character in cycle 2 has already reached the target, so this research was stopped in cycle 2.

Conclusion

The conclusion of this research is that applying model of mobile web based on character building in teaching learning process involving preparation, core, and closing activities of teaching learning process can improve student character related to student love of learning, perseverance, and prudence for 30 students Grade five at Cempaka Putih Timur 03 Public Elementary School in Jakarta in Indonesia.

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